

A PRELIMINARY NOTE ON MESUOL, THE BITTER PRINCIPLE OF *MESUA FERREA*.

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The bitter fatty oil of the seed kernel of *Mesua ferrea*, Linn. (*N. O. Guttiferae*), known in India as Nagkesar or Nageshwar oil, has been the subject of a number of investigations (Boorsma, *Bull. Inst. Botan. Buitenzorg*, 1904, 21, 4; Hooper, *Pharm. J.*, 1908, 27, 161; Grimme, *Chem. Rev. Fett. Harzind.*, 1910, 17, 156; Dhingra and Hilditch, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 50, 97; Chatterjee and Gupta, *Oil Col. Trades J.*, 1937, 91, 1656). Very little is, however, known regarding the other constituents of the seeds. Boorsma (*loc. cit.*) reported the presence of two resinous bitter principles, but they did not receive further attention.

Chatterjee and Gupta (*loc. cit.*) observed that Nageshwar oil produces a deep yellow colour in contact with dilute aqueous alkali. This phenomenon is characteristic of the oil, and it must be due to some principle other than the normal constituents of a vegetable oil. It had moreover been observed by previous investigators that the expressed oil deposited a solid 'stearin' on keeping. Microscopic examination of this deposit revealed the presence of a crystalline substance, which was found to dissolve in aqueous alkali with a deep yellow colour. Obviously the 'stearin' is responsible for the production of the yellow alkali salt. We thought it desirable to examine the crystalline substance in greater detail. The want of a suitable hydraulic press led us to attempt its isolation from the oil extracted by means of solvents. The best results have been obtained by a method which is detailed in the Experimental. The pure compound, obtained in a yield of nearly 1%, formed pale yellow, transparent prisms, m.p. 154°. It is apparently different from the amorphous principles isolated by Boorsma. The name 'Mesuol' is proposed for this substance which appears to be a new one.

Mesuol is neutral to litmus and has a slight bitter taste. It is soluble in 1% aqueous alkali, 10% ammonia and hot sodium carbonate solutions, but insoluble in sodium bicarbonate. Acids precipitate the compound unchanged from the deep yellow alkaline solutions. The colour with ferric chloride in alcohol medium is dirty olive-green. Mesuol is obviously phenolic in character. It is optically inactive, and is free from methoxy and

methylenedioxy groups. The yellow colour of mesuol in alcohol is deepened on the addition of lead acetate, but no precipitate is formed. Treatment with hydrochloric acid and metallic magnesium did not produce any colour. It is evidently not a hydroxyflavone. The analytical and M. W. data agreed with the formula, $C_{23}H_{22}O_5$ or $C_{22}H_{20}O_5$. The analytical values of dimethylmesuol, however, lend support to the former. We, therefore, tentatively assign the molecular formula, $C_{23}H_{22}O_5$, to mesuol.

The dimethyl derivative, just referred to, was obtained in quantitative yield by methylation of mesuol with methyl iodide in acetone medium in presence of potassium carbonate. Dimethylmesuol is indifferent to ferric test, but showed the presence of lactone ring. Methylation with diazomethane does not proceed to complete methylation of the two phenolic OH groups of mesuol.

The elucidation of the structure of mesuol by further experiments which are in progress will form the subject of a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Mesuol.—The seeds of *M. ferrea* were collected from the district of Sylhet in Assam. The kernels of the air-dried material were coarsely powdered and extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 40-50°) in a large Soxhlet during 18 hours. The reddish brown extract was freed from the major part of the solvent and allowed to stand at about 20° for several days. After three weeks the crystalline deposit of crude mesuol was collected and freed from adhering fat by washing with petroleum ether in which mesuol is almost insoluble. The product was then repeatedly crystallised from methyl alcohol, benzene-petroleum ether and dilute acetone in succession. The first crop of crystals from the last named solvent usually formed yellow, opaque, feathery crystals, m. p. 152°, which were rejected. Mesuol separated from dilute acetone as pale yellow, compact, transparent prisms, m. p. 154°. Further crystallisations failed to alter the m. p. Purified by distillation at 190-200°/0.04 mm. and subsequent crystallisation from methyl alcohol, it had the same m. p. [Found in samples dried at 110° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 72.7, 72.7; H, 6.2, 6.02. M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 377, 378. $C_{22}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 72.53; H, 5.5 per cent. M. W. 364. $C_{23}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 73.03; H, 5.82 per cent. M.W., 378).

Mesuol is readily soluble in warm alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform and pyridine, moderately in carbon bisulphide and sparingly in ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a greenish yellow colour. It is insoluble in concentrated hydrochloric acid.

Dimethylmesuol.—To mesuol (0.2 g.), dissolved in dry acetone (15 c.c.), were added methyl iodide (0.4 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.5 g.). The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 5 hours. The orange-yellow colour of the solution faded to straw-yellow after completion of the reaction. The solution was freed from insoluble potassium salts and evaporated to dryness. The oily residue solidified on treatment with a little methyl alcohol in the cold. The crystals were collected, washed with water and recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 131°. Further purified by distillation in high vacuum (170-75°/0.04 mm.) and subsequent crystallisation from ligroin, it formed colourless prisms or plates, m.p. 132°. [Found in samples dried at 110° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: C, 73.7; H, 6.49 per cent. M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 407. C₂₅H₂₆O₅ requires C, 73.88; H, 6.4 per cent. M. W., 406].

Dimethylmesuol is soluble in most organic solvents but not in water. Its alcoholic solution turned deep yellow on the addition of 10% aqueous alkali, but the colour faded to pale apple-green on keeping or warming. Dilution of the alkaline solution did not give any precipitate. On adding mineral acids an oil separated out, which solidified on keeping overnight. Crystallised from methyl alcohol it melted at 132° alone or when mixed with dimethylmesuol. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is greenish yellow.

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